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A USER-CENTERED ASSESSMENT OF THE USABILITY OF DIGITAL GAME DEVICES FOR UPPER EXTREMITY REHABILITATION THERAPY

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ABSTRACT

Rehabilitation device is an essential tool in the process of rehabilitation therapy. Some therapists have tried to use the existing digital game devices in rehabilitation and found effective treatment outcomes in addition to enhancing the patient's treatment motivation. However, these existing devices are originally designed for normal people with healthy physical and action conditions, not intended for rehabilitation therapy purposes or for people with physical disabilities. Further confirmation and evaluation is necessary to see if a digital game device can really meet the user's usability needs in addition to its rehabilitation effectiveness. The objective of this study is to understand the types of the existing digital game devices which have been used in clinical treatments, and to evaluate their usability in rehabilitation therapy by means of the user-centered design concept, and to summarize a guideline for the improvement design of such devices. Following are some guidelines for the design improvement related to these devices: a) To increase the response time of the games, b) To increase difficulty levels of the games, c) To expand the sensor's sensing scope, d) To be able to record movement data, e) To provide a Chinese version of the software interface of the games, f) To improve the ways to fix the controller on the user's hand, g) To fit the controllers to the different hand dimensions of the patients, h) To provide better correspondence between the games and real-life movements, i) To provide controllers for body control training, j) To simplify the controller's operation.

Keyword: user-centered design, usability assessment, digital rehabilitation device

INTRODUCTION

Stroke is one type of the cerebrovascular disease threatening people in modern societies. For instance, cerebrovascular disease has become the top three causes of death in the United States (Heron, 2009). In Taiwan, such diseases also are the third cause of death for the year 2010 (Department of Health, Executive Yuan of R.O.C., 2011). According to statistics, the majority patients for occupational therapy in hospitals are stroke patients (Department of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation in NTUH, 2010).

The main cause of stroke is also due to cerebrovascular diseases. Stroke patients usually suffer motor deficits in the extremities, also known as paraplegia or hemiplegia. Stroke patients with brain injury would show motor and perception defect in the opposite side of the body (Sawner & LaVigne, 1992). Such patients would have motor impairment of the cooperative movement, postural reflex and joint response and other physical symptoms. Upper-extremity motor deficit is one of the main symptoms for the stroke patients (Gowland et al., 1992). About 85% stroke patients have function impairment on upper-extremity at the beginning stage of the stroke, and still about 40% patients have function impairment at the final stage of stroke (McCrea et al., 2002). Many daily living tasks are performed by the upper extremity; therefore, rehabilitation

treatment of upper extremity is very important for stroke patients.

In order to restore the movement function of patient's upper extremity, patients must accept the rehabilitation activities. Rehabilitation device is an essential tool in the process of rehabilitation therapy. A study (Huang et al, 2010) has found that the current clinical upper extremity rehabilitation devices are mostly static, and provide no feedback to the patients. Patients easily feel boredom while repeating the same activity, hence generating a negative attitude toward the therapy process. In order to increase mental satisfaction and physical vitality in rehabilitation therapy, some therapists have tried to use the existing digital game devices in rehabilitation and found effective treatment outcomes in addition to enhancing the patient's treatment motivation (Broeren et al, 2004; Stewart et al, 2007; Reinkensmeyer & Housman, 2007). However, these existing devices are originally designed for normal people with healthy physical and action conditions, not intended for rehabilitation therapy purposes or for people with physical disabilities. Further confirmation and evaluation is necessary to see if a digital game device can really meet the user's usability needs in addition to its rehabilitation effectiveness.

There are many studies related to use digital game intervention in rehabilitation. For example, A feasibility study using four VR tasks that were developed and tested to improve arm and hand movement skills for individuals with hemiparesis (Stewart et al., 2007). The result show that the less impaired participant averaged more time on task, practiced a greater number of blocks per session, and progressed at a faster rate over sessions than the more impaired participant. Impairment level did not change but both participants improved functional ability after training. The less impaired participant increased the number of blocks moved on the Box & Blocks test while the more impaired participant achieved 4 more items on the Functional Test of the Hemiparetic upper extremity.

Develop a therapeutic device (Therapy WREX) that individuals with substantial arm weakness and

minimal hand function after stroke can use to improve their movement ability without the continuous presence of a rehabilitation therapist (Reinkensmeyer & Housman, 2007). Initial clinical testing indicates that chronic stroke patients can significantly improve their movement ability with T-WREX. We have also found that patients strongly prefer using T-WREX for therapy compared to conventional, self-directed, tabletop exercises. Virtual Reality and Haptics as a Training Device for Movement Rehabilitation After Stroke (Broeren et al., 2004). Improvements were found in fine manual dexterity, grip force, and motor control of the affected upper extremity. The subject reported that there was a change in his day-to-day use of the upper extremity and that he was able to use it in activities that were previously impossible for him. To investigate the effectiveness of computerized virtual reality training of the hemiparetic hand of patients poststroke using a system that provides repetitive motor reeducation and skill reacquisition (Merians et al., 2006). The result show that subjects as a group improved in fractionation of the fingers, thumb and finger range of motion, and thumb and finger speed, retaining those gains at the 1-week retention test.

Most of the mentioned studies focus on the efficacy of the digital game device intervention in rehabilitation, but currently very few focus on evaluate the usability and user satisfaction of existing digital game devices. Basically, a good digital game device for upper extremity rehabilitation should conform to the therapy purposes according to the patients' upper extremity action status. Furthermore, it should enhance the pleasure and motivation of the patients. Therefore, design a digital game rehabilitation device to better satisfy the user needs and therapy purposes is necessary.

User-centered design emphasizes that designers observe the behavior and situation of the actual user's experience, that is, how users use a product and what problems and needs exist. About the medical and rehabilitation equipment should be evaluated for effectiveness, ease of use, comfort, and acceptability (Jacobs, Karen, 2008). Through

design, these problems can be solved and the redesigned product would then meet the user's needs. In order to design a good digital game device for upper extremity rehabilitation to better satisfy the user needs, first, we must understand the current using situation of the products in clinical. Therefore, the objective of this study is to evaluate the usability of the existing digital game devices in rehabilitation therapy for stroke patients by means of the user-centered design concept, and to summarize a guideline for the improvement design of such devices.

METHODS

This study uses the method of expert interview to conduct a survey of the current situation of the use of digital game devices and evaluate the usability of such devices in upper extremity rehabilitation therapy. This section summarizes the locations, participants, process, and contents of the interview.

There are some hospitals in Taiwan that have adopted digital game intervention in rehabilitation. The selection criteria for the interview subjects were mainly based on the hospital size, type (public vs. private), geographic location, and types of digital games used. Two hospitals were selected in a preliminary investigation: Taipei Veterans General Hospital (TVGH) and Kaohsiung Veterans General Hospital (KVGH).

Occupational therapist plays a major role in the rehabilitation process to determine how the digital game device is used. Although each the digital game device has its intended functions, not necessarily the patients can perform the treatment movements directly by themselves. In general upper extremity rehabilitation treatment, a professional occupational therapist would assess the patient's upper extremity situation, then select the digital game device with appropriate functions and design a series of therapy activities to meet the specific patient's requirement. As a professional, the occupational therapist possesses expertise about therapy theory and experiences, which are useful for the evaluation of rehabilitation devices. The usage assessment of the digital game devices by therapists is very important for the improvement and redesign of existing digital

game devices for better function as well as performance. Therefore, in this research stage, occupational therapists are the main target group of the investigation. Selection criteria for the interviewed therapists were: 1) at least 5 years work experience in occupation therapy, and at least one year experience in adopting the digital game device intervention in rehabilitation treatment. In total, eight therapists were selected and interviewed, three (one male [A] and two females [B, C]) from KVGH and five (two males [D, E] and three females [F, G, H]) from TVGH. They have an average age of 35.1 yrs (SD=6.3) and work experience of 10.8 years (SD=6.3).

Semi-structured interviews were used, which mainly consist of three parts: 1) Therapist personal profile - therapist gender, age, hospital name, and work experience in years, 2) Types of digital gaming device used in clinical, and 3) Questions about the usability evaluation of existing digital gaming device: The questions are:

- Q1. Device Type: What type of digital game devices do you use in rehabilitation?
- Q2. Effectiveness: How do you feel about the therapy effectiveness of the devices in restoring the patient's upper extremity functions?
- Q3. Ease of Use: Do you have any usage problems in setting up the devices to be used for therapy? What needs to be improved in the design of the devices?
- Q4. Comfort: According to your professional judgment, is it comfort for the patient to operate the controller of the device?
- Q5. Acceptability: How do the patients response to the use of digital game devices in rehabilitation? Do they accept it and like it?

Appointments were made before the researcher visited the Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation Department of the hospitals. In the interviews, the researcher would firstly explain the purpose of this study to the therapists. The therapists were asked to fill out their personal profile, then they were asked the above mentioned questions one by one and

answer each of them based on the professional knowledge and working experience regarding to the use of digital game device in rehabilitation. In the mean time, the researcher audio-recorded the described responses and asked for clarification of ambiguous points, if any, for subsequent result analysis.

RESULTS

To analyze the interview data, the recording was firstly transcribed to verbatim. Then, according the two digital game devices used (Wii and Xavix), the opinions were thus summarized separately for further comparison. Similar opinions were combined and all unique responses were independently itemized for further discussion. The results corresponding to the interview questions were summarized as follows:

1. Device Type: What type of digital game devices do you use in rehabilitation?

There are two types of existing digital game devices used in rehabilitation, Wii and Xavix. Wii is used in Kaohsiung Veterans General Hospital and Xavix is used in Taipei Veterans General Hospital. The console, controller, and sample game projects of these devices are summarized in Table 1.

For Wii, it primarily includes a host console and a handheld controller (called Remote, which is rectangular shaft with several buttons on the top and a switch on the bottom). Game projects currently often adopted by therapists in the rehabilitation are: Wii Fit and Wii Sport. The Wii Sport usually is played by operating the Remote in rehabilitation. The Wii Fit, however, has to be played with the Wii Balance Board. The Remote and/or the Balance Board interact with the Console via Bluetooth wireless technology. Not only operations on the Remote, but also the movements of the Remote itself, as well as the Balance Board, can be detected by the Console.

As for Xavix, it includes a host console and a variety of controllers of different forms for different game projects for different trainings, such as social skills training, attention training, eye coordination training with hands and feet, memory and visual perception

training, memory training, etc. The TVGH has collected Xavix's all available 30 game projects. Each of them comes in a system cartridge with a sensor camera. The infra-red sensor in the console, the camera on the cartridge, and the reflective film on the controller work to detect the movements of the operation done by the user. To date, however, not all these game projects have been used by TVGH for rehabilitation.

2. Effectiveness: How do you feel about the therapy effectiveness of the devices in restoring the patient's upper extremity functions?

Clinically, in order to let the patient safely use the digital game device in rehabilitation, professional occupational therapists would assess the holding capability of the patient's hand and its movement stability. Patients with upper extremity motor

Table 1 Types the digital game devices currently used in rehabilitation

	Wii	Xavix
Console		
Controller		
Game Project	 Wii Fit	

Picture origin: <http://uk.wii.com/>
<http://www.xavix.com/products/index.html>

functions achieving Brunnstrom's recovery stages 4 and 5 are considered as capable of holding the controller and keeping up with the game actions, and thus would be recommended for using the Wii Sport for higher level movement training of the upper extremity. Wii Fit, on the other hand, is used for balance therapy regardless of the function of the upper extremity.

For the therapy effectiveness of the Wii, all three therapists (A, B, and C) agree that the Wii Sport is effective in upper extremity rehabilitation performances, in addition to enhancing the patient's treatment motivation. In addition, Therapist A suggests that Wii Fit is especially suitable for balance therapy for stroke patients.

For the therapy effectiveness of the Xavix, all five therapists (D, E, F, G, H) agree that the device is effective in upper extremity rehabilitation, and can enhance the patient's treatment motivation and pleasure. D also comments that some of the game projects with their controllers can effectively strengthen the training of reaching and grasping movements and achieve better therapy effectiveness as compared to that of the traditional devices. For instance, when the patient wears the gloves as controllers in the Xavix games, his/her hands are required to actually do the reach and grasp movements to complete the game task. In so doing, the training of the hands in those movements are apparent and practical.

The results of these interviews found that therapists have positive opinion about the effectiveness of the digital gaming device intervention in rehabilitation, and the improvement of patient motivation toward the treatment. In addition, therapists E and F mentioned that the existing traditional therapy devices are still important in rehabilitation therapy and not possible to be fully replaced by digital gaming rehabilitation devices. The traditional rehabilitation devices do not require the patient to react in time and restrict his/her movement speed, hence the patient can repeat the movement as many times as he/she wishes and at a speed at his/her own control. Therefore, the digital game device can play a supporting role in rehabilitation treatment by

providing diversification and interesting game projects for improvement of patient motivation toward the treatment.

3. Ease of Use: Do you have any usage problems in setting up the devices to be used for therapy? What needs to be improved in the design of the devices?

For the Wii, all three therapists (A, B, C) consider that the device is easy to set up, except some errors may occur when setting the game software items. The usage problems of this device are:

- 1) The current software interface is in Japanese and not easy to understand, hence is prone to cause errors in the set-up process;
- 2) The required response time of the game is too fast and not easy to keep up with by the patients;
- 3) Some patients may have difficulty to hold the hand controller, hence need additional bandage to tie it on the hand;
- 4) For some patients, the games are slightly too difficult.

The suggested improvements in design are:

- 1) To provide better hand-controller interface, e.g., easy and solid method of fixing the controller to the hand;
- 2) To allow flexible and adjustable response time of the games;
- 3) To provide adjustment of the difficulty level of the games.

For Xavix, all five therapist agree that the hardware is easy to set up, except the software interface operation may cause occasional mistakes. The usage problems of this device are:

- 1) The current software interface is in Japanese and not easy to understand, hence is prone to cause errors in the set-up process, especially for the games of visual perception and memory training, which are impossible to operate without literacy of the Japanese language;
- 2) The sensor is not sensitive enough, e.g., the action may obstruct the reflective film and interrupt the detection by the sensor;
- 3) The controller gloves have only one single size, do not necessarily fit to all patients;

- 4) Although the games are available in three levels of difficulty, the differences between the difficulties are too abrupt and hard to meet the patient's required degree of difficulty.

The suggested improvements in design are:

- 1) To increase difficulty levels of the games in order to better suit the various patients with different abilities of upper extremity function;
- 2) To expand the sensor's sensing scope in order to allow a wider movement space of the users
- 3) To be able to record movement data, such as: reaction time, operating time, etc.;
- 4) To fit the controllers to the different hand dimensions of the patients;
- 5) To provide better correspondence between the games and real-life movements;
- 6) To provide controllers for body control training, such as chest strap and belt.

From the interviews, it is found that the Xavix is a digital game device specially designed for the elderly, the games and their corresponding controllers are diverse, each with different levels of difficulty. Nevertheless, there are still a number of points which need to be further improved.

4. Comfort: According to your professional judgment, is it comfort for the patient to operate the controller of the device?

The result shows that, for both Wii and Xavix, none of the eight therapists has received any complaints from the patients concerning discomfort in operating the controllers. However, therapist A commented that the controller of Wii often drop off from some patients' hand even with the safety ring held around the wrist. Therefore, he proposed that the controller can be designed to be bolder in size or to have a banding strap to help the patient to hold it. Some patients can not press the buttons on the controller to operate the menu due to incomplete recovery of the hand functions, hence need to be assisted by the therapist for such operations before they can proceed into the game. Therefore, it is desirable to redesign the interaction mode between the controller and the game. For Xavix, therapist D suggested that this device provides a different set of controllers, which are suitable for different forms of

motor training for the patients. For instance, the use of gloves, bowling, and other controllers can be useful for training the hand grip function.

5. Acceptability: How do the patients response to the use of digital game devices in rehabilitation? Do they accept it and like it?

The result shows that all eight therapists agreed that most patients can accept the use of Wii or Xavix for treatment. Therapist B explained that people interested in the game have a very high degree of acceptance of such devices. However, some elderly patients tend to prefer using the traditional rehabilitation devices, because they feel that the traditional devices are some physical objects that can be held and manipulated, hence giving a feeling of the effect of treatment. On the contrary, digital game devices give an impression of laxness and frivolity, and hence are inefficient and ineffective.

IMPROVEMENT DESIGN OF THE DIGITAL GAME DEVICES

From the results obtained from the interviews, it is found that the digital game devices currently used in clinical rehabilitation have been evaluated by professional therapists as useful and effective in supporting the treatment. However, some design improvements may be necessary in order to enhance their usability in terms of their interface with the patients. Based on the result of the above interviews, design guidelines concerning the improvement of existing digital game devices can be synthesized as follows, where items a-e are about software design, and items f-j about hardware:

- a) To increase the response time of the games.
- b) To increase difficulty levels of the games in order to better suit the various patients with different abilities of upper extremity function.
- c) To expand the sensor's sensing scope.
- d) To be able to record movement data, such as: reaction time, operating time
- e) To provide a Chinese version of the software interface of the games.
- f) To improve the ways to fix the controller on the user's hand.

- g) To fit the controllers to the different hand dimensions of the patients.
- h) To provide better correspondence between the game and real-life movements,
- i) To provide controllers for body control training, such as chest strap and belt.
- j) To simplify the controller's operation.

CONCLUSION

In order to increase mental satisfaction and physical vitality in rehabilitation therapy, some therapists have tried to use the existing digital game devices in rehabilitation and found effective treatment outcomes in addition to enhancing the patient's treatment motivation. However, these existing devices are originally designed for normal people with healthy physical and action conditions, not intended for rehabilitation therapy purposes or for people with physical disabilities. Further confirmation and evaluation is necessary to see if a digital game device can really meet the user's usability needs in addition to its rehabilitation effectiveness. This report mainly presents the results of the preliminary interviews with occupational therapist on the clinical use of existing digital game devices in rehabilitation. Conclusions can be summarized into the following points:

- 1) Therapists have positive opinion about the effectiveness of the digital gaming device intervention in rehabilitation, and the improvement of patient motivation toward the treatment.
- 2) Therapists consider that patients generally are willing to use the digital game for rehabilitation. Only some elderly patients tend to prefer using the traditional rehabilitation devices, because they feel that the traditional devices are some physical objects that can be held and manipulated, hence giving a feeling of the effect of treatment.
- 3) From the viewpoint of rehabilitation needs, the existing digital gaming devices still need to be improved in their design. Following are some guidelines for the design improvement related to these devices:

- a) To increase the response time of the games,
- b) To increase difficulty levels of the games,
- c) to expand the sensor's sensing scope,
- d) To be able to record movement data,
- e) To provide a Chinese version of the software interface of the games,
- f) To improve the ways to fix the controller on the user's hand,
- g) To fit the controllers to the different hand dimensions of the patients,
- h) To provide better correspondence between the game and real-life movements,
- i) To provide controllers for body control training, such as chest strap and belt,
- j) To simplify the controller's operation.

From the result of the expert interviews, it is concluded that digital game devices have been in use in Taiwan in the field of rehabilitation and occupational therapy. This paper reports the current situation of the use of such devices. More comprehensive follow-up investigation would be necessary in order to conduct an assessment of the usability of such devices, so as to propose design improvements of them in order to enhance their treatment effectiveness as well as their acceptance by the users.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This study is supported by the National Science Council of the Republic of China with grant No: NSC 99-2221-E-040-009.

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